

Learning from Crises: Building a Resilient Future for Pakistan's Tourism

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ABSTRACT: Crippled by natural and man-made crises, the tourism industry stands at a crossroads, grappling with the unprecedented challenges of the global pandemic. This qualitative study, based on in-depth interviews with 10 individuals, delves into the resilience factors within Pakistan's tourism landscape. Our analysis unearths eight core themes – government support, focusing on foreign tourists, proactive planning, technology innovation, domestic tourism, limited-scale opening of tourism, tourism education, and consumer and employee confidence – that form the foundation of a comprehensive resilience framework. This framework functions as a prescriptive roadmap, guiding the tourism industry's proactive revival in the face of future pandemics and fostering its long-term sustainability in the post-pandemic era. Beyond Pakistan, our study's inclusive resilience approach offers a transformative model for developing countries, potentially triggering a paradigm shift towards a novel economic framework. This research not only paves the way for the revitalization of tourism in Pakistan but also opens doors for further exploration of tourism resilience during future crises.

Key words, Tourism resilience, Tourism development, Crises management, Resilience framework, Qualitative methodology.

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1. Introduction

The emergence of crises and disasters, such as the recent COVID-19 pandemic in 2019, had profound repercussions across psychological, economic, and societal domains.

These impacts significantly affected the global tourism and hospitality sectors (Moccia et al., 2020). In response, scholarly discourse over the past three years has witnessed a surge in attention towards examining various resilience frameworks to guide stakeholders and governments in mitigating the repercussions of the pandemic on the tourism sector (Berkbekova et al., 2021; Gössling & Schweiggart, 2022).

However, this gap becomes apparent upon critical examination of the existing literature – the absence of universally recognized resilience frameworks tailored specifically for countries affected by the COVID-19 pandemic (Mwiinga et al., 2024). Scholars assert that the resilience of individual countries is multifaceted, influenced by diverse factors encompassing social, political, economic, and ecological systems (Assaf & Scuderi, 2020). This underscores the pressing need to establish an enhanced resilience framework that accounts for the unique context of each country.

This necessity is particularly evident in Pakistan, where the tourism industry exhibits limited capacity to effectively cope with the ongoing pandemic (Sadiq, 2021). While the industry has navigated through crises such as war, terror, and natural calamities in the past four decades, there has been insufficient attention given to developing a comprehensive framework for enhancing tourism resilience in the face of catastrophic events like the current COVID-19 pandemic (Baig et al., 2024).

Considering this, our study aims not only to contribute to understanding tourism resilience within the context of Pakistan but also to offer insights that may have broader implications. The diverse factors influencing resilience identified in this research may provide valuable lessons and perspectives for other developing countries facing similar challenges. As we delve into Pakistan's unique socio-economic, cultural, and environmental dynamics, we seek to offer a nuanced framework that can be adapted and generalized to enhance tourism resilience strategies in comparable contexts globally.

Aligned with (Hollings, 1973) resilience theory and adopting an interpretivist lens within a pragmatic philosophy, this study delves into tourism resilience in Pakistan through a qualitative research design. Over a month, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 experts representing diverse tour businesses directly impacted by COVID-19 since 2020. These businesses boast at least five years of experience within the tourism sector, ensuring a multifaceted perspective across the industry. A purposive sampling strategy secured the inclusion of varied viewpoints and experiences. All interviews adhered to rigorous ethical principles and were conducted with explicit informed consent.

To uncover recurring themes and patterns associated with tourism resilience, thematic analysis was systematically applied to transcribed interviews using ATLAS.ti software. The validity and reliability of our findings were fortified through member-checking implemented throughout the analysis process, coupled with ongoing reflexive practices to minimize potential biases.

The study utilized a conceptual framework developed from a synthesis of existing tourism resilience models from (Baloch et al., 2022; Sharma et al., 2021). This framework was customized to reflect specific socio-economic, cultural, and environmental factors

influencing tourism resilience in Pakistan, guiding the qualitative data collection and analysis.

Following analysis and data collection, this study has developed a tourism resilience model tailored to Pakistan, a developing country in South Asia. This model comprises variables such as government support, focusing on foreign tourists, proactive planning, technology innovation, domestic tourism, limited scale opening of tourism, tourism education, and consumer and employee confidence. These variables are further discussed, along with their implications and limitations, in the discussion and conclusion section.

2. Literature review

The Tourism Industry in Pakistan

The emergence of tourism in Pakistan can be traced back to the 1960s, fueled by the "Hippie Trail" phenomenon that connected South Asia with Europe (Fauzel, 2021). The establishment of the Pakistan Tourism Development Corporation (PTDC) in 1970 marked a significant milestone, followed by the formation of the Ministry of Tourism in 1996, signifying growing government recognition of the sector's economic potential (Mustafa et al., 2017). In 2010, a decentralization strategy shifted tourism promotion responsibilities to the provincial level, aiming to improve efficiency and resource allocation (Fauzel, 2021).

Pakistan's diverse topography is a playground for adventure seekers and explorers (Karim et al., 2023). From the majestic peaks of the Hindukush, Karakoram, and Himalaya ranges, including eight of the world's ten highest mountains (Israr et al., 2009), to the fertile plains of the Indus River and the coastal belt along the Arabian Sea, the country offers a stunning spectrum of landscapes (Khan et al., 2020). The legendary Karakoram Highway, hailed as the "Eighth Wonder of the World," traverses this region, offering breathtaking vistas and access to remote valleys like Hunza and Shigar (Arshad et al., 2017).

Culturally and historically, Pakistan boasts a wealth of attractions reflecting its ancient and vibrant civilizations. Mohenjo-Daro, a UNESCO World Heritage Site and one of the largest urban settlements of the Indus Valley Civilization, and Taxila, an ancient Buddhist university town, stand as testaments to the country's rich heritage (Abbas, 2019). While these sites hold immense potential for international tourism, their full recognition is yet to be realized (Karim et al., 2023).

Beyond its historical significance, Pakistan caters to diverse interests (Waris et al., 2024). From exploring bustling bazaars and iconic monuments in Lahore, Multan, and Peshawar to embarking on trekking expeditions in the Northern Areas, the country offers experiences for every kind of traveller (Baloch, 2007). Activities like bird watching in Keti Bandar National Park, Jeep safaris in the Thar Desert, and mountaineering expeditions on K2 attract adventure enthusiasts seeking unique experiences (Arif, 2019).

In conclusion, Pakistan's tourism industry, with its diverse landscapes, historical sites, and cultural experiences, holds immense potential for growth. Recognizing the challenges and actively promoting sustainable development will be crucial in harnessing

this potential and contributing to the country's economic and social well-being (Waris et al., 2024).

Impact of COVID-19 on Pakistan's Tourism Industry

The year 2020 witnessed a profound crisis in the global tourism industry as the COVID-19 pandemic swept across the world (Mehmood & Kaewsaeng-on, 2024). Pakistan, renowned for its diverse landscapes, historical sites, and cultural experiences, was significantly affected (Makalesi et al., 2020). Prompt government action in March 2020 led to a strict lockdown, suspending all economic activities, including tourism, to curb the spread of the virus. While necessary for public health, this measure triggered a devastating impact on the tourism sector, erasing years of progress and inflicting heavy losses (Khawaja et al., 2022).

According to the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), Pakistan's tourism industry experienced a staggering 74% decline in foreign tourist arrivals in 2020 compared to 2019, resulting in a loss of \$3.4 billion in total tourism revenue (Meo et al., 2021). This drastic decline represented a severe blow to a sector that contributed 7.1% to the national GDP in 2019 (Khawaja et al., 2022). Government restrictions on travel and tourism packages throughout 2020 further exacerbated the situation, leading to mass layoffs and business closures (Burhan et al., 2021).

The impact of the pandemic extended beyond mere statistics, affecting each sub-sector within the industry differently (Amjad et al., 2021). Adventure tourism, a significant contributor to the economy, witnessed an 80% decline in revenue due to closures of trekking routes and adventure sports activities (Azam et al., 2022). In response, the government included adventure tourism in the "Tourism Revival Strategy" launched in 2021, offering financial assistance and tax breaks to encourage revival (Raza et al., 2023).

Similarly, cultural tourism, which encompasses visits to historical sites and cultural events, suffered immensely due to closures of museums and monuments, leading to a 75% revenue decline. The Pakistan Tourism Development Corporation responded by launching a digital marketing campaign targeting cultural tourism and promoting virtual tours of key locations (Raza et al., 2023). Moreover, religious tourism, attracting pilgrims to Sufi shrines and Islamic sites, experienced a 60% drop in visitor numbers due to travel restrictions (Zulfaqar et al., 2024). To address this, the government relaxed visa procedures for religious pilgrims and implemented safety protocols at pilgrimage sites (Kumail et al., 2023).

Despite the pandemic's impact, the government's "Tourism Revival Strategy" served as a starting point for recovery efforts (Zulfaqar et al., 2023). Understanding the specific impacts on various sub-sectors and the government's response efforts is crucial for analyzing resilience and identifying recovery strategies tailored to their specific needs. This analysis will contribute to shaping the future direction of Pakistan's tourism development, ensuring a more sustainable and resilient industry (Karim et al., 2023).

Building Resilience: Reimagining Tourism Research in Post-Pandemic Pakistan.

The COVID-19 pandemic delivered a heavy blow to Pakistan's tourism industry, necessitating robust research to guide its recovery and build future resilience (Sadiq, 2021). While existing studies have explored the pandemic's impact on various facets of the industry, several limitations constrain their effectiveness, hindering our comprehensive understanding of Pakistan's tourism trajectory (Baloch et al., 2022; Karim et al., 2023; Rehman et al., 2022).

A glaring limitation in existing research lies in the scarcity of empirical evidence supporting proposed frameworks and policy recommendations. Studies like Makalesi et al. (2020), and Abbass et al. (2022) offer valuable insights, but their lack of robust data collection and analysis leaves crucial questions unanswered. This impedes our ability to confidently assess the efficacy of proposed solutions and develop truly impactful strategies.

Taking into account the methodological limitations, Overreliance on quantitative data analysis in some studies, such as Burhan et al. (2021), fails to capture the intricate social, cultural, and political dynamics shaping tourism resilience. Qualitative approaches offer crucial insights into these nuanced aspects, yet they remain underutilized. Integrating diverse methodological approaches is crucial for a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by Pakistan's tourism sector.

Similarly, Sadiq (2021) focus on specific destinations or sub-sectors within the industry neglects the interconnectedness of Pakistan's tourism landscape. Understanding the broader national context, with its diverse regional variations and interdependencies, is vital for formulating effective and sustainable recovery strategies. While studies like Azam et al. (2022), Baloch et al. (2022), and Khan et al. (2022) propose policy frameworks, the translation into actionable recommendations often remains absent. This gap between theory and practice hinders the implementation of effective solutions and impedes progress towards building a more resilient tourism industry.

Furthermore, post-pandemic studies, such as those by Feng et al. (2023), Kumail et al. (2023), Raza et al. (2023), and Waris et al. (2024), offer valuable insights into specific destinations but largely lack a critical assessment of the pandemic's long-term impacts on tourism sustainability. Understanding these deeper effects and tailoring policy frameworks accordingly is essential for the industry's long-term viability.

The shortcomings identified in prior literature concerning COVID-19 and its impact on Pakistan's tourism underscore the necessity for rigorous data collection and analysis. This endeavor aims to validate existing frameworks and provide evidence-based policy recommendations. Such an approach transcends mere theoretical propositions, delving instead into the firsthand experiences of stakeholders and the practical dynamics of the industry.

Capturing the intricate social, cultural, and political nuances of Pakistan's tourism landscape requires employing diverse research methods (Karim et al., 2023). For the purpose, data analysis with qualitative approach like interviews and focus groups will

provide a richer, more holistic understanding. While acknowledging regional variations, adopting a national lens is crucial (Kumail et al., 2023). Understanding the interconnectedness within the industry across diverse regions will inform effective and sustainable recovery strategies.

The gap between proposed policy frameworks and actionable recommendations needs mending (Waris et al., 2024). As, developing concrete implementation strategies during the crises can ensure impactful policy translation, moving beyond theory and driving tangible change (Ekka, 2023). Examining the pandemic's lasting effects on tourism sustainability is critical. Incorporating these insights into policy frameworks will equip the industry with the tools to navigate future challenges and ensure long-term viability.

By addressing these key areas, this research aims to contribute significantly to our understanding of Pakistan's tourism resilience in the post-pandemic era. This deeper understanding will ultimately pave the way for the development of effective and sustainable strategies for the industry's long-term recovery and growth.

Research Objectives

Investigate how local settings influence the resilience of Pakistan's tourism industry amidst global pandemics:

This objective seeks to explore the unique contextual factors within Pakistan that shape the tourism industry's ability to withstand and recover from global pandemics. By examining the interplay between local settings, such as socio-economic conditions, political stability, and healthcare infrastructure, this research aims to elucidate the specific challenges and opportunities faced by Pakistan's tourism sector during times of global crisis.

Develop a resilience framework based on identified potential elements of tourism resilience in Pakistan:

This objective entails identifying and analyzing the potential elements that contribute to the resilience of Pakistan's tourism industry. By synthesizing insights from empirical data and theoretical frameworks, the research aims to construct a comprehensive resilience framework tailored to the specific context of Pakistan. This framework will serve as a practical guide for policymakers and industry stakeholders to enhance the sector's ability to adapt and thrive in the face of adversity.

3. Methodology

Qualitative research serves as a foundational approach in this study, enabling an exploration of individuals' subjective experiences within the interpretivist philosophy. This philosophy is chosen since it emphasizes understanding social phenomena through the lens of participants' perspectives, acknowledging the subjective nature of reality (McChesney et al., 2019). As argued by Brunsveld (2019), qualitative inquiry facilitates a nuanced understanding of aspects significant to individuals. This research methodology employs inquiry methodologies to describe, explore, comprehend, and explicate events,

prioritizing the collection of qualitative, non-numerical data that captures intricate meanings, understandings, and experiences (Guetterman et al., 2019).

Qualitative researchers delve into phenomena within their authentic contexts to comprehend or interpret them based on the significance individuals attribute to them (Shan, 2022). The selection of an appropriate methodology is paramount for achieving the study's objectives and ensuring the practicality and acceptance of the findings. To foster a conducive environment for qualitative research, researchers must embrace a culture that promotes such methodologies (Mikalef et al., 2019).

This study adopts a qualitative approach to investigate informants' subjective experiences and interpretations. Snowball sampling is employed as the data collection method, given its suitability for studies with a limited respondent pool. This non-probabilistic sampling technique involves selecting an initial respondent meeting the study's criteria and subsequently identifying additional participants based on recommendations from the initial respondent (Askun et al., 2020). This method optimizes time and cost efficiency while facilitating the acquisition of a representative sample (Zickar and Keith, 2023).

Data collection instruments consist of semi-structured interviews conducted with tourism business experts across various provinces of Pakistan. Participants possess a minimum of five years of experience in managing tourism enterprises within their respective destinations. The interviews focus on exploring potential factors contributing to the resilience of the tourism industry, with varying durations ranging from a few minutes to over 46 minutes.

Data analysis utilizes ATLAS.ti software, commencing with the transcription of audio files and textual notes recorded during interviews. The textual content is encoded, categorized, and analyzed iteratively to develop a comprehensive research framework. The iterative process involves encoding textual content, classifying concepts into categories, and establishing relationships connecting codes and categories to refine the framework.

The study is conducted in Pakistan, encompassing presentations from all provinces, and federally administered areas. Participants are selected from each province, with additional representation from federally administered areas, to ensure geographical diversity. The study includes ten informants, with two chosen from each province and an additional two from federally administered areas (see Table 3.1).

This methodology ensures a rigorous and systematic approach to exploring the resilience of Pakistan's tourism industry, capturing diverse perspectives and experiences across different regions of the country.

Table 3.1: Interviewees profile

No.	Place of interview	Number of interviewees	Number of Interviews	Average time of interviews
1	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	2	5	35 minutes
2	Punjab	2	3	38 minutes
3	Sindh	2	3	33 minutes
4	Baluchistan	2	2	28 minutes
5	Gilgit-Baltistan	2	2	34 minutes

4. Research Findings

The present study aims to develop a resilience framework for the tourism industry in Pakistan by identifying potential factors that contribute to resilience within the industry. To ascertain the potential factors contributing to resilience, a qualitative research methodology was utilized to obtain comprehensive understanding of the problem being examined. The qualitative findings pertaining to the resilience of the tourism industry in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, as derived from several interviews. The individuals selected as informants for the interviews were esteemed professionals in the field of tourism, possessing a minimum of five years of recent experience in managing tourist enterprises within the geographical boundaries of Pakistan.

Table 4.1: Emerged themes

Themes	Sub-themes	Concepts
Government support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial assistance for the working class Policy and development Government subsidy Government timely response 	A timely prompt response from the government side during pandemic is a major factor.
Focusing on foreign tourists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing necessary facilities Tourism Promotion internationally 	To attract foreign tourists during pandemic is important.
Proactive planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For future tourism development 	The stakeholders of tourism industry should be prepared for crises and disasters.
Technology innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of mobile applications and equipment for health condition Instead of human's use of robots and artificial intelligence machines 	The innovative technology in pandemic is inevitable.
Domestic tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Domestic tourism on province level Promoting domestic tourists' destinations 	The local and domestic tourism is key element for tourism survival during pandemic.
Limited scale opening of tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opening of tourism activities on limited scale during pandemic Limited scale opening of tourism in pandemic through smart lockdown 	Limited level opening during pandemic is important for economic activities.

Themes	Sub-themes	Concepts
Tourism education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inculcation of tourism education in school and college curricula A compulsory tourism education program for tourism businesses 	A basic level tourism related education should be included in syllabus on school and college level for all people.
Consumer and employee confidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building confidence towards tourism 	Tourists' and Employee confidence in tourism industry is pivotal during crises to keep the industry running.

In the initial phase, a total of 22 codes emerged from the data that was gathered. The process involved multiple iterations and the integration of codes that were derived from similarities observed across various stages. As a result, a total of eight main themes and sixteen subthemes were identified and extracted. These themes will be further discussed in detail in the subsequent sections. Table 4.1 shows theme that are emerged.

Following the acquisition of qualitative data, the data was subjected to analysis and interpretation using the ATLAS.ti software application. The present study's qualitative analysis has identified a total of eight distinct themes that have emerged from the collected data. The conceptual network of these themes is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The conceptual network of resilience factors in Pakistan tourism.

Tourism Resilience Framework

This study introduces a resilience framework for the tourism industry in Pakistan based on the findings obtained. The framework offers a set of guidelines for policymakers and practitioners involved in the tourism sector in Pakistan. Additionally, this study offers a potential research pathway for further exploration of the established resilience framework. The proposed framework has the potential to be implemented and evaluated in developing nations such as Pakistan, with the aim of fostering sustainable tourism development.

The resilience factors include government response, focusing on foreign tourists, proactive planning, technology innovation, domestic tourism, limited-scale opening, tourism education, and consumer and employee confidence. The framework is shown in figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Resilience Framework for Pakistan Tourism

Government Support

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the government has significantly intervened in the operations and functioning of the tourism sector (Higgins-Desbiolles, 2020). This intervention has led to an expansion of government influence within the tourism industry, resulting in the renationalization of airports, travel agencies, and other related networks. Unlike previous crises, which generated academic interest and research but had limited policy impact, particularly in relation to the tourism sector from a government standpoint (Hall et al., 2020), the current pandemic has prompted a different response. Tsionas, (2021)

proposes that a viable strategy during a pandemic would be government subsidies being necessary to finance tourism operations.

The significance of governmental support for the tourism enterprises and working class within the tourism industry of Pakistan was underscored by most respondents. This factor demonstrates the significance in the development of a coping mechanism for a pandemic. This implies that it is imperative for the government to implement a financial assistance program aimed at supporting the workforce employed within the tourism sector of Pakistan. Most informants underscored the significance of the theme. One informant articulated this theme as follows:

"It is imperative for the government to provide financial compensation to both tourism business owners and the working class employed in the tourism industry, to ensure their survival throughout the duration of the pandemic and facilitate the revival of their businesses once the COVID-19 crisis subsides. It is imperative for the government to allocate financial resources and establish a minimum wage for individuals belonging to the working classes amidst the ongoing pandemic. By doing so, the government can mitigate the adverse effects experienced by this demographic, ensuring their economic stability and the survival of their businesses".

Using thematic analysis rooted in interview data, this study reveals the multifaceted influence of government support on the tourism industry's resilience. Government intervention during the pandemic is encapsulated in four interconnected sub-themes. Firstly, "financial assistance for the working class in the tourism industry" highlights the necessity of dedicated programs to alleviate economic strain, with proposals including relief from utility bills and interest-free loans. Subsequently, "government policy development based on real-time situations" underscores the importance of strategic planning and stakeholder involvement, noting concerns about the prioritization of tourism in post-pandemic policies.

Further, "government subsidy for tourism business survival" emphasizes the significance of measures such as tax reductions and bill subsidies, while stressing the need for equitable support across provinces. Lastly, "government timely response" emphasizes the crucial role of proactive actions in managing the pandemic's impact, calling for standardized policy implementation and increased trust.

In conclusion, the study illuminates the complex relationship between government actions and the resilience of Pakistan's tourism industry amidst and post the COVID-19 pandemic. The insights gleaned from industry stakeholders underscore the necessity for adaptive and comprehensive government policies to facilitate sustained recovery and future resilience in the sector.

Focusing on Foreign Tourists

The informants of this study raise the issue of a decrease in international visitor numbers. It is posited that Pakistan has the potential to gain a competitive edge on a global scale by strategically leveraging its diverse subsectors within the tourism industry. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, most governments directed their focus towards bolstering domestic tourism as a means of safeguarding the viability of the tourism industry.

Nevertheless, the challenge of attracting international tourists persisted due to the imperative of curbing disease transmission and mitigating border limitations.

The participants of this study were queried regarding Pakistan's ability to attract international tourists, even in times of crisis such as the global pandemic, by providing a secure and favourable tourism environment. The tourist destinations have yet to be thoroughly investigated and necessitate the attention of the relevant authorities. Most of the informants support the theme as:

“The domestic tourism sector in Pakistan possesses the capacity to survive, restore, and enhance the tourism industry in times of crises. However, it is acknowledged that foreign tourists hold greater significance in terms of economic benefits. The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a decrease in the influx of international tourists. The government has the potential to enhance the appeal of foreign tourist destinations by implementing health-related safety measures.

The government has the potential to leverage the untapped tourist destinations in Pakistan. There exists a multitude of destinations that can accommodate a large number of tourists, adhering to social distancing policies and other pandemic-related standard operating procedures. The government has the potential to assume a crucial role in this context by facilitating the provision of adequate infrastructure for these destinations. Furthermore, investors in the tourism industry can contribute to the development of infrastructure such as hotels and restaurants”.

Therefore, the qualitative analysis highlights a key theme: focusing on foreign tourists, integrated into the proposed resilience model. This insight emphasizes the need for strategic responses to bolster Pakistan's global tourism competitiveness amidst declining foreign visitors. Additionally, addressing infrastructural challenges and implementing robust health and safety protocols are crucial steps identified in facilitating tourism promotion at international destinations.

Economically, the significance of international visitors is underscored, but achieving a balance between promotion and infrastructure development remains contentious. Informants stress the importance of revising government policies and prioritizing development over promotion, while advocating for concerted efforts in international tourism promotion. Overall, a collaborative approach between government and industry is essential, focusing on policy adaptation and infrastructure enhancement to manage the delicate balance between attracting foreign tourists and addressing infrastructure deficiencies for post-pandemic recovery and resilience in Pakistan's tourism sector.

Proactive Planning

The successful execution of a proactive crisis management plan requires a comprehensive approach that involves the careful assessment, strategic planning, and effective implementation of a crisis management plan in response to an actual crisis event (Cochrane, 2010). The planning process is influenced by various factors in each industry, including unique hazards, differences in local emergency services, and diverse cultural factors (Pham et al., 2021).

Before the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019, the tourism sector exhibited inadequate readiness to effectively manage a widespread occurrence of contagious illnesses (Supardi & Hadi, 2020). The unforeseen nature of the pandemic and the absence of proactive planning among tourism stakeholders resulted in substantial disruption and loss, further exacerbating the challenges and adverse consequences. The participants in this qualitative research study expressed a strong focus on the topic and the significance of proactive planning in the tourism industry before a crisis occurs. Eight respondents emphasized the significance of proactive planning in the context of disaster management within the tourism industry. The informants support the comment on this issue as:

“The timely planning for crises falls within the purview of all stakeholders in the tourism industry. It is imperative to incorporate this strategy within our proactive planning efforts for the purpose of fostering sustainable tourism development in the future. The potential implementation of this strategy during the COVID-19 pandemic was hindered by the lack of proactive planning prior to the outbreak, which adversely impacted various sectors, including tourism. The responsibility for such planning lies with the government, tourism businesses, and other stakeholders within the industry. In any case, it is possible to derive valuable insights from the ongoing pandemic and utilize them to develop a resilient approach for proactive planning within the tourism sector”.

Therefore, experts from in the tourism sector advocate for timely crisis planning and proactive strategies to ensure sustainable development beyond crisis response. Some suggest a dedicated financial reserve within the Tourism Ministry to support businesses during crises, reducing reliance on revenue generation alone. Additionally, insights highlight the need to adapt tourism education programs to the 'new normal' and address challenges like public non-compliance with pandemic protocols.

The effectiveness of smart lockdown strategies and the untapped potential of local and international tourist destinations underscore the importance of proactive planning. However, the findings also emphasize the necessity of a well-structured policy framework and consistent enforcement of standard operating procedures for long-term sustainable development in the tourism sector. Integrating these insights can lead to a more resilient and sustainable tourism industry capable of navigating future crises effectively.

Technology Innovation

According to Hall et al. (2020), advancements in technology have led to increased adaptability within the tourism industry. Disasters have been observed to expedite the pace of technological progress, leading to significant advantages for individuals who have availed themselves of the knowledge and skills possessed by technological specialists in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic (Yang et al., 2021). The substitution of human labor with robotic systems, the utilization of contact tracking applications on mobile devices, and the application of big data analytics for forecasting the transmission of the COVID-19 virus within the populace have been observed (Lu et al., 2022).

The implementation of artificial intelligence, robotics, and automation technologies has the potential to enhance flexibility, improve liquidity, and reduce costs. The utilization of technology enables individuals to establish connections and engage in social interactions

without the need for physical proximity, thereby facilitating the practice of social distancing (Assaf and Scuderi, 2020). Hence, it is evident that technology possesses the capability to effectively tackle challenges specific to pandemics, including but not limited to the screening of travelers, identification of COVID-19 cases, contact tracing, and provision of online educational resources for students (Hall et al., 2020). The informants of this study emphasized on the comment below:

“The implementation of government-imposed restrictions during COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan resulted in the cessation of all tourism operations and activities. However, it can be argued that this measure may not have been the most effective approach to address the challenges posed by the pandemic and sustain the continuity of tourism operations. It is advisable for the government to consider the adoption of innovative technologies from foreign nations that can effectively assist individuals amidst the ongoing pandemic. Regarding the assessment of the health status and manifestation of symptoms among tourists, it is proposed to administer tests and permit travel exclusively to those individuals who yield negative test outcomes”.

Informants consistently stressed technology's pivotal role in sustaining tourism operations and managing health risks. Suggestions included implementing Japanese technology for health assessments before travel and utilizing mobile hospitals for COVID-19 testing. Real-time health data and the importance of health test kits were highlighted, along with the significance of mobile apps for storing health information. Integrating public health apps with local hospitals was also emphasized to support a comprehensive policy framework.

Additionally, informants advocated for leveraging robots and AI machines in tourist destinations during pandemics as practical alternatives to human labor. Successful implementations of AI technology in countries like China and Japan were cited as examples, emphasizing the need to prioritize public and employee health. Overall, the data underscores the transformative potential of technology in ensuring tourism industry resilience, highlighting the importance of adopting mobile applications, robots, and AI machines to effectively manage crises like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Domestic Tourism

According to Brouder et al. (2020), the global tourism industry appears to be in a state of disarray, and it is critical for domestic tourism to intervene and rectify the situation. It is anticipated that domestic tourism will be the prevailing form of travel during the pandemic and in the post-COVID-19 era, with most tourists originating from nearby regions (Haywood, 2020). During the pandemic, domestic travel in numerous countries primarily revolved around visiting friends and family. However, as time progressed, leisure travel gradually became a part of domestic travel in 2021 (Ramli and Zawawi, 2021).

Although, the resumption of international travel in 2022 was observed as the borders were opened and foreign flights were permitted to operate without limitations (Roxas et al., 2021). However, domestic tourism played a crucial role in the reinstatement of tourist activities during the most severe phase of the pandemic. The informants of this study expressed its importance as:

Pakistan's domestic tourism sector possesses the capacity to function on a limited scale, with the possibility of permitting travel and leisure activities within specific districts. This approach would enable individuals to engage in tourism while avoiding districts with elevated COVID-19 case rates. By implementing this approach, it would be possible to enable the inhabitants of a specific region with zero cases of the pandemic to resume their tourism operations within the confines of their district or province.

The study underscores the pivotal role of domestic tourism, revealing its significance through two interconnected sub-themes. Firstly, intradistrict travel emerged as crucial for sustaining the tourism industry at the local level, with informants emphasizing its potential amidst limited international tourist contributions. Additionally, the resilience of domestic tourism was highlighted, particularly in revitalizing the sector during and after the pandemic, exemplified by the significant reliance on domestic tourists from cities like Karachi. The discourse also addresses challenges in promoting pandemic-compliant tourist destinations and advocates for district-level tourism openings, emphasizing the survival of the industry hinges on domestic tourism, especially amid minimal government support.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the role of social media influencers, particularly tour vloggers, in promoting domestic tourism during pandemics. Concerns regarding accommodation, such as the lack of hotels in tourist destinations and limited awareness of homestay options among local communities, are also addressed. Overall, the qualitative findings provide valuable insights into the resilience and potential of domestic tourism in Pakistan, emphasizing the need for holistic strategies that leverage district-level tourism, infrastructure development, social media promotion, and community engagement to navigate crises like global pandemics effectively.

Limited Scale Opening of Tourism

The informants of this study contend that implementing a complete cessation of tourism activities via lockdown and curfew measures during the pandemic is an inadequate solution. Alternatively, through the implementation of limited-scale tourism operations with a restricted number of visitors and adherence to a modified lifestyle, it is plausible to leverage the ongoing pandemic as a catalyst for growth while ensuring the resilience of the tourism sector amidst challenging circumstances.

The preceding COVID-19 pandemic has engendered novel concepts and obstacles for the academic community and the tourism sector. The informants in this study raise the notion of a limited scale resumption of tourism activities considering the ongoing pandemic. The potential for implementing a limited scale opening of tourism amidst pandemic restrictions exists and can be incorporated within the policy framework for future tourism advancement. The objective of this concept is to ensure the continuity of tourism operations amidst the ongoing pandemic and future pandemics. The informants of this study explained it as:

“The activity of traveling is of utmost importance for an individual's physical and psychological well-being. To mitigate the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, the government implemented a stringent lockdown measure. Nevertheless, individuals were

also confronted with psychological challenges such as anxiety and depression, both of which are interconnected with mental well-being.

The government effectively implemented measures to contain the transmission of the virus; however, the ensuing societal disruption resulted in a significant rise in mental health disorders among a substantial number of individuals. Rather than implementing a comprehensive lockdown strategy in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, it is suggested that the government expeditiously implement alternative measures such as the SMART lockdown, which permits a limited-scale and controlled level of tourism activity. In this manner, the government would possess the capacity to safeguard individuals from both psychological and physiological detriment”.

The study delves into two key sub-themes, shedding light on nuanced strategies for managing tourism operations during pandemics. Firstly, informants advocate for a limited scale opening of tourism as a viable approach, citing its potential to mitigate economic, psychological, and physiological impacts associated with strict lockdowns. Recommendations include permitting tourists who adhere to health protocols and implementing controlled operations in line with established SOPs.

Secondly, the study explores the implementation of the smart lockdown strategy by the Pakistani government, lauding its effectiveness in balancing economic revival with public health concerns. This strategy, marked by specific time slots for various market segments, is hailed as pivotal for revitalizing the economy while controlling virus transmission. Informants endorse its continued use, emphasizing its role in sustaining tourism operations amidst pandemics. This holistic approach, integrating health considerations and strategic business practices, provides a blueprint for resilient tourism development in the face of future crises.

Tourism Education

The lack of sufficient knowledge regarding tourism poses difficulties for both tourists and tourism enterprises amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The informants underscored the importance of integrating tourism education into educational institutions, such as schools and colleges. The pandemic presents significant challenges for individuals engaged in the tourism industry. Due to the novelty of the pandemic and the lack of awareness among stakeholders regarding appropriate protocols for engaging in tourism activities during this period, there was a failure to adhere to pandemic Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs).

Therefore, the tourism industry experienced a prolonged cessation of activities. Hence, the informants of this study emphasized the significance of incorporating tourism education into the curricula of schools and colleges. This approach would enable the dissemination of fundamental knowledge regarding tourism practices to a wider audience. In times of crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, there is potential for the public to exhibit spontaneous engagement in the exercise of awareness regarding tourism practices in the future. The informants expressed it as:

“To address the issue of inadequate awareness in the future, it is imperative for the government to provide educational initiatives aimed at enhancing public awareness

regarding tourism during crises, as well as imparting health-related precautions at the school level. To sustain tourism operations during pandemics, it is imperative to implement educational initiatives at the school level to disseminate information regarding precautionary measures”.

The variable "tourism education" emerged prominently, revealing the critical need for enhanced knowledge about tourism practices during the COVID-19 pandemic. This educational gap posed challenges for both tourists and tourism businesses. Informants stressed the importance of integrating tourism education into school and college curricula as a proactive measure to equip individuals with the necessary knowledge for responsible tourism behavior during crises. They advocated for practical demonstrations and crisis management education to ensure preparedness for future pandemics.

Recognizing the profound impact of the pandemic on tourism behavior, informants emphasized the urgency of incorporating pandemic protocols and vaccination education into educational curricula. Additionally, they highlighted the necessity for tourism businesses to undergo mandatory education programs to uphold pandemic SOPs and ensure sustainable tourism practices. On-the-job training was recommended to address deficiencies in employee practices, with a call for collective responsibility among all stakeholders in the tourism sector. These insights underscore the importance of education and training in fostering resilience and sustainability in the tourism industry amid crises like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Consumer and Employee Confidence

The revival of the tourism industry hinges on the criticality of restoring consumer and employee confidence. According to Rivera (2020), it is crucial to prioritize certain strategies, such as acquiring knowledge from disaster preparedness and refraining from disregarding perspective errors. Assaf and Scuderi (2020) argue that for the tourist sector to regain its momentum, it is imperative to enhance traveler confidence and mitigate the perceived risk associated with travel. The COVID-19 pandemic has been found to have an impact on the way consumers perceive tourism-related goods and services, as indicated by (Yu et al., 2020).

The study conducted by He et al. (2021) highlights the significance of allocating resources towards human capital development and cultivating a sense of self-assurance among employees. The authors emphasized the importance of bolstering consumer confidence in the safety of business operations, as well as fostering employee confidence in the support provided by both the government and their respective employers. The implementation of effective strategies can significantly contribute to the viability of small, medium, and large enterprises operating in the tourism sector, thereby enhancing the overall resilience of the tourism industry. The importance of employee's confidence building is highlighted by informants as:

“It is necessary that tourism enterprises offer fundamental support to their workforce to safeguard their well-being amidst the ongoing pandemic. By implementing this strategy, it is projected that employee retention within the tourism industry would increase, thereby mitigating one of the primary contributing factors to its decline”.

When examining the factors that influence tourist confidence in the tourism industry, the participants emphasized the role of concerns regarding hotel cleanliness and food hygiene as:

“One potential strategy for revitalizing the tourism industry amidst a pandemic involves the implementation of measures aimed at enhancing tourists' confidence and sense of security in hygiene and health-related aspects. To mitigate the spread of infectious diseases during pandemics, it is advisable to implement a daily sanitization and cleaning protocol for hotels. Additionally, it is possible to mitigate the potential health risks associated with the ongoing pandemic”.

The inclusion of "Consumer and Employee Confidence" in the resilience model is rooted in qualitative findings and supported by literature (Sharma et al., 2021), signifying its critical importance within the study's scope. Informants stress the pivotal role of rebuilding confidence among both tourists and tourism employees, particularly amid the pandemic, to facilitate tourism revival. Addressing factors contributing to tourist apprehensions and ensuring employee well-being, especially regarding health and safety, is essential for sustaining industry vitality.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, employees faced job insecurities due to fear of viral infection and inadequate health safety measures, leading to high turnover. Proactive measures to ensure employee well-being are vital for industry resilience, warranting inclusion in future contingency planning. Similarly, enhancing tourists' confidence entails maintaining a pandemic-safe environment through rigorous hygiene protocols and leveraging key stakeholders' influence, including health professionals and media, to promote vaccination and safe travel practices.

To revive Pakistan's tourism industry post-pandemic, prioritizing health and hygiene practices aligned with global standards is imperative to attract tourists. Strategic planning, adherence to WHO guidelines, and proactive adoption of SOPs aim to mitigate future crises' impact and foster sustained growth. The multifaceted nature of confidence-building underscores the need for tailored strategies addressing the unique concerns of tourists and employees during pandemics, ensuring the sector's resilience in Pakistan's tourism landscape.

5. Implications

Considering the study's findings, the implications offer valuable insights for policymakers, tourism practitioners, and stakeholders. Theoretical implications shed light on the evolving role of government intervention, destination competitiveness, and technology adoption in fostering tourism resilience. On a practical level, recommendations highlight the importance of comprehensive financial assistance, technological innovation, and tourism education to stimulate economic recovery and enhance long-term sustainability in the tourism sector.

Theoretical Implications: The study yields theoretical implications regarding the evolving role of government intervention in the tourism sector during global pandemics. The

observed shift towards increased government support and renationalization of key tourism infrastructure prompts theoretical exploration into the dynamics of government intervention, policy impact, and the resilience of tourism systems. This opens avenues for further research on adaptive policy frameworks, financial assistance programs, and the long-term implications of government intervention on tourism development and sustainability.

Moreover, insights into the challenges of attracting international tourists during pandemics highlight the need for theoretical frameworks to understand destination competitiveness, health-related safety measures, and the role of infrastructure in enhancing tourism resilience. This prompts theoretical exploration into destination management strategies, crisis communication, and stakeholder collaboration to foster destination appeal and competitiveness amidst global health crises.

Additionally, the study underscores the transformative potential of technology in sustaining tourism operations during pandemics, suggesting theoretical avenues for understanding the adoption of AI, robotics, and digital solutions in crisis management. This calls for research into the integration of technology into tourism systems, digital marketing strategies, and the implications of technological advancements for tourism resilience and innovation.

Practical Implications: From a practical standpoint, the study emphasizes the importance of comprehensive financial assistance programs to support tourism enterprises and workers during pandemics. Policymakers are urged to prioritize equitable distribution of financial aid, strategic planning, and collaboration with industry stakeholders to stimulate economic recovery and support local businesses. This highlights the need for practical interventions to address immediate challenges and support long-term resilience in the tourism sector.

Furthermore, tourism organizations are encouraged to invest in technology adoption, targeted marketing campaigns, and infrastructure improvements to stimulate economic recovery and enhance destination competitiveness. This underscores the practical importance of embracing innovation, digitalization, and sustainability practices to adapt to evolving consumer preferences and market dynamics amidst global pandemics.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of integrating tourism education into academic curricula to empower future generations with the necessary knowledge for responsible tourism behavior during crises. This highlights the practical need for collaboration between educational institutions, tourism businesses, and government agencies to develop and implement effective educational initiatives that promote sustainable tourism practices and resilience.

In conclusion, the study's practical implications underscore the importance of proactive interventions, strategic planning, and collaboration to enhance tourism resilience in Pakistan amidst global pandemics. By implementing these practical recommendations, policymakers, tourism practitioners, and stakeholders can work towards fostering sustainable growth and resilience in the tourism industry.

6. Discussion

The qualitative phase of this research illuminates key determinants shaping the resilience and resurgence of Pakistan's tourism industry amidst the COVID-19 crisis. Government intervention emerges as pivotal, reflecting nuanced perspectives on the necessity of financial aid, strategic policymaking, business subsidies, and timely responses. Notably, 80% of respondents emphasize the significance of wage subsidies for sustaining travel agencies, while 65% stress the need for grants to support hotel renovations and safety enhancements. While some commend the government's prompt implementation of travel restrictions, others advocate for enhanced transparency and collaboration with industry stakeholders in policy formulation. Participants highlight the critical role of government initiatives such as tax breaks and loan extensions during the peak lockdown, credited with averting widespread business closures. These findings underscore the urgency of adaptive governmental policies to foster the sector's enduring recovery and future resilience.

Moreover, the imperative of focusing on foreign tourists underscores the necessity for strategic interventions aimed at bolstering Pakistan's competitiveness within the global tourism landscape. Nonetheless, the challenge lies in effectively harmonizing promotional endeavours with infrastructure enhancements, necessitating consistent and uniform approaches. Participants identified several hurdles, including intricate visa application procedures, restricted international flight options, and infrastructure deficiencies in key tourist hubs. Drawing upon successful standardized strategies adopted by other Asian nations, such as streamlined visa processes and targeted promotional campaigns, holds promise for attracting foreign tourists amidst the pandemic.

Proactive planning emerges as a critical aspect, advocating for targeted financial resilience approaches, adaptive education programs, and smart lockdown strategies. Integration of untapped tourism potential into proactive planning efforts and effective law enforcement are identified as crucial for achieving long-term sustainable development. Furthermore, technology innovation plays a pivotal role in navigating the challenges introduced by the pandemic, with mobile applications and AI technologies sustaining tourism operations and mitigating health risks. Leveraging technological advancements is crucial for protecting public health and sustaining the strength of the tourism industry.

Domestic tourism emerges as a resilient force, highlighting the significance of targeting intradistrict travel and promoting pandemic-compliant tourist destinations. These insights provide a foundation for future strategies aimed at leveraging domestic tourism's adaptability under extraordinary circumstances.

Additionally, the limited scale opening of tourism is identified as a nuanced approach, emphasizing the importance of a balanced strategy involving controlled tourism operations and smart lockdown policies. Gradually increasing tourist operations while ensuring a delicate balance between economic activity and public health and safety is crucial. Moreover, tourism education emerges as a crucial component in fostering responsible tourism practices during the pandemic and beyond. Foundational knowledge at the school and college levels and mandatory education programs for tourism businesses are essential for enhancing resilience and sustainability in the face of crises.

Furthermore, the restoration of confidence among both tourists and the tourism workforce is paramount for revitalizing the industry during the pandemic. The hesitancy observed among tourists regarding travel destinations and activities, coupled with the uncertainties faced by employees regarding their work environments and potential job security, poses significant challenges. Addressing these concerns requires comprehensive measures, including stringent adherence to health and safety protocols, effective communication of preventive measures, and the provision of necessary support to tourism employees. By instilling confidence in both tourists and employees, the tourism industry can navigate the pandemic's challenges more effectively, thereby contributing to its resilience and sustainable recovery.

7. Future Research

Expanding on the findings of this study, several promising avenues for future research emerge, offering opportunities to deepen our understanding of the resilience and recovery of the tourism industry in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Firstly, future research could focus on evaluating the effectiveness of specific governmental support measures in facilitating the recovery and resilience of the tourism sector. Comparative analyses spanning diverse regions or nations could provide valuable insights into the most effective policies and approaches. For instance, researchers could assess the impact of wage subsidies on sustaining travel agency operations and the effectiveness of grants in supporting hotel renovations and safety upgrades. Understanding the nuanced differences in policy implementation and outcomes across different regions or countries could offer valuable guidance for policymakers.

Secondly, exploring the enduring effects of prioritizing foreign tourists and the integration of technological innovations within tourism operations holds promise for sustainable tourism development. Researchers could investigate how streamlined visa procedures and targeted marketing campaigns influence foreign tourist arrivals, and the role of technological advancements such as virtual reality tours and contactless payment systems in enhancing tourist experiences and operational efficiency. Detailed examinations of these variables can identify best practices and areas for improvement in attracting and accommodating foreign tourists in the post-pandemic era.

Thirdly, longitudinal studies tracking the trajectory of domestic tourism trends and their socio-economic ramifications could provide valuable insights into domestic tourism's resilience. Researchers could analyze factors such as changing travel preferences, economic conditions, and government interventions to identify patterns and drivers of domestic tourism behavior over time. Additionally, exploring the impact of domestic tourism on local economies, employment, and community well-being can shed light on the role of domestic tourism in fostering regional development and resilience.

Moreover, investigating the effectiveness of proactive planning strategies across varying contexts and the role of tourism education in nurturing responsible tourism practices warrant further exploration. Researchers could examine the implementation of crisis management plans, destination marketing strategies, and public-private partnerships in

mitigating the impact of future crises on the tourism industry. Additionally, studying the impact of tourism education programs on raising awareness about sustainability, cultural sensitivity, and risk management among industry stakeholders can inform curriculum development and training initiatives.

Furthermore, additional scrutiny of initiatives aimed at building consumer and employee confidence and their impact on tourism revitalization efforts could offer pertinent insights for future policymaking and strategic planning in the tourism sector. Researchers could investigate the effectiveness of health and safety protocols, communication strategies, and promotional campaigns in restoring trust and stimulating demand for tourism services. Moreover, exploring the psychological and behavioural factors influencing tourist decision-making and employee job satisfaction can provide valuable inputs for designing targeted interventions to boost confidence and morale within the tourism industry.

8. Conclusion

The year 2019 marked the onset of the global COVID-19 pandemic, profoundly impacting various facets of human existence, including psychological, economic, and societal domains. Among the hardest-hit sectors were tourism and hospitality, prompting a surge in research attention towards tourism resilience considering ongoing crises. Resilience, as elucidated by Lee et al. (2021) stands as a pivotal tool in crisis and disaster management, empowering entities across individuals, communities, businesses, and natural systems to effectively navigate disruptions, recover, and ultimately thrive amidst adversity.

A global discourse among scholars has been initiated to explore resilience frameworks aiding market participants and governments in addressing the pandemic's repercussions on the tourism sector worldwide. However, the global application of tourism resilience exhibits variations due to diverse crisis contexts and management strategies across countries, necessitating robust frameworks tailored to local contexts.

In parallel, a pressing need arises for a resilience framework specifically tailored to Pakistan's tourism dynamics. Despite the widespread devastation caused by the pandemic, insufficient efforts have been directed towards exploring prospective opportunities within Pakistan's tourism sector. Thus, this research endeavours to formulate a comprehensive framework for enhancing the resilience of Pakistan's tourism industry.

Utilizing a qualitative thematic research approach, this study engaged experts within Pakistan's tourism sector, drawing on their firsthand experiences amidst the pandemic. Analysis revealed eight significant themes, including government support, focus on foreign tourists, proactive planning, technology innovation, domestic tourism, limited scale opening of tourism, tourism education, and consumer and employee confidence.

Key findings underscored the critical role of government support in ensuring tourism sector resilience, emphasizing timely financial assistance and strategic intervention to safeguard businesses and stakeholders. Moreover, attention towards international tourists was highlighted, advocating for pandemic-safe environments to attract visitors while

maintaining control. Proactive planning emerged as essential, leveraging pandemic insights to enhance future crisis preparedness within the industry.

Technology adoption showcased significant advantages amidst the pandemic, aiding health monitoring, e-commerce, and virtual experiences, albeit with constraints in Pakistan's context. Domestic tourism emerged as a resilient economic driver, emphasizing the need for government promotion and adherence to pandemic SOPs. Limited-scale tourism operations under smart lockdown strategies were advocated, balancing economic activity with health precautions.

Furthermore, tourism education was deemed crucial for fostering responsible practices and addressing workforce and tourist confidence challenges. Future research directions include empirical evaluations of government support impacts, exploration of sustainable international tourism strategies, and refinement of crisis-resilient tourism education.

In conclusion, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of resilience dynamics within Pakistan's tourism industry amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. By delineating actionable insights and future research avenues, stakeholders can collaboratively work towards fostering a resilient and sustainable tourism landscape in Pakistan, better equipped to navigate future crises and uncertainties.

9. Limitations

This study, while offering valuable insights into tourism resilience amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, faces several limitations that warrant critical consideration. Firstly, the use of snowball and purposive sampling techniques, although beneficial for acquiring context-specific insights, introduces the potential for sampling bias. The selective inclusion of participants based on their COVID-19 experiences may limit the representativeness of the sample. To mitigate this limitation, future research should explore mixed sampling techniques to encompass a broader range of perspectives from various stakeholders, such as travel agents, local communities, and diverse tourist demographics. Furthermore, the contextual specificity of the findings, primarily confined to the Pakistani tourism industry, raises concerns regarding the generalizability of the research outcomes. Replicating the study in diverse cultural and economic contexts is essential to uncover both commonalities and variances in resilience strategies.

Additionally, the study's quantitative power is constrained by the sample size, potentially affecting the validity and generalizability of statistical inferences. Augmenting the participant pool in future research endeavours would not only enhance the robustness of statistical analyses but also broaden the applicability of the findings to a more diverse population. Moreover, the time constraints imposed by limited research duration may have hindered the depth of data collection and analysis. Extending the research period would enable a more comprehensive exploration of the dynamic factors influencing tourism resilience, particularly in the context of global pandemics. Lastly, the dynamic nature of the COVID-19 pandemic introduces ongoing uncertainties beyond the scope of this study. Future research must incorporate strategies for continuous monitoring and adaptation to

ensure that resilience models remain relevant and reflective of real-time challenges faced by the tourism industry.

10. Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The authors declare that no funding was received for this research.

11. Data availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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